

Learning Styles as Predictors of Learner Literacy Skills in Grade 2

Sheryl Mae O. Revilla

Abstract. This study aimed to determine how learning styles predict the literacy skills of Grade 2 learners in Laak North District, Division of Davao de Oro. A quantitative descriptive-correlational method was employed, with data gathered from 150 Grade 2 public school teachers. The learning styles examined were visual, auditory, and kinesthetic, while literacy skills were assessed in terms of reading, writing, speaking/listening, and assessment. The findings revealed that all three learning styles were evidently observed among learners, and all dimensions of literacy skills were consistently practiced and reinforced by teachers. Statistical results indicated a significant positive relationship between learning styles and literacy skills. Furthermore, regression analysis showed that each learning style significantly influenced literacy outcomes, with kinesthetic learning emerging as the strongest predictor. These results underscore the importance of recognizing and addressing diverse learning preferences in designing literacy instruction for early grade learners. The study highlights the role of differentiated, learner-centered strategies in supporting foundational literacy development. These findings may provide relevant insights for curriculum developers, school administrators, and educators in tailoring teaching methods that align with learners' dominant styles.

KEY WORDS

1. Learning styles 2. literacy skills 3. predictors

Date Received: April 05, 2025 — Date Reviewed: May 15, 2025 — Date Published: June 18, 2025

1. Introduction

Learners' literacy skills in grade 2 presents considerable challenges for the fact that learners exhibit diverse preferences such as visual, auditory, kinesthetic, or tactile learning, and aligning instruction with these preferences within a classroom setting proves complex. Understanding and accommodating various learning styles pose substantial obstacles in anticipating literacy skills among learners in grade 2. Additionally, the influence of socio-economic factors and individual differences further complicates the relationship between learning styles and literacy skills, highlighting the ongoing difficulties educators face in addressing the diverse needs of grade 2 learners. In Ecuador, second-grade learners face significant difficulties in developing core literacy skills, particularly in transitioning from basic reading to deeper comprehension. Many struggle to extract meaning from texts, which hinders their academic growth across subjects. These literacy challenges are especially evident in reading comprehension, vocabulary acquisition, and inferential thinking. Such difficulties have been docu-

mented among Ecuadorian elementary learners (Benitez-Correa et al., 2022). In Bangladesh, the development of literacy skills among Grade 2 learners is often hindered by several challenges, including difficulties in sustaining attention during reading and writing tasks. Maintaining focus is essential for literacy growth, yet many young learners struggle with this foundational requirement. Additionally, disparities such as learning difficulties and limited access to print-rich environments at home further compound these issues. These factors collectively contribute to the persistent literacy challenges faced by Bangladeshi second-grade students (Hassan Sen, 2019). The U.S. education sector continues to grapple with alarming literacy challenges, particularly among early-grade learners. Recent data from the National Center for Education Statistics show that millions of American students face persistent reading difficulties, with many failing to reach basic proficiency levels. National assessments reveal that only 35% of students in the Philippines, particularly in Panabo City, Davao del Norte, Grade 2 literacy education is confronted with several pressing challenges that impede effective learning outcomes. A significant number of learners begin the school year struggling to grasp foundational reading concepts, which makes instructional progress difficult for educators. Teachers are further burdened by limited classroom resources, including insufficient access to quality reading materials and educational technology. These barriers collectively hinder the creation of a supportive and stimulating literacy environment for young learners (Thomas et al., 2020). Also, in Cagayan de Oro City, classrooms that do not effectively accommodate diverse learning styles often struggle to keep learners engaged and motivated. As a result, learners develop misconceptions about basic concepts, making it difficult for them to solve problems and sustain interest in extended academic tasks. Reports revealed that 27.5% of learners in General Santos City, many learners in public

elementary schools continue to face significant difficulties in achieving expected literacy outcomes. One major reason is that these learners have yet to fully develop essential learning skills necessary for reading comprehension and written expression. Assessment results revealed that learners only attained an average mean score of 65.02. Also, Filipino learners were among the lowest performing groups among all the participating countries in the 2018 Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA). Overall, less than 20% of learners locally, in the researcher's setting in Davao de Oro, poor literacy and numeracy skills of grade 2 learners have been noted as evident on their low performance in past three years. Those learners who were poorly guided and who weren't exposed with their dominant learning styles showed less interest towards learning and exhibited low level of literacy attainment. This unpleasant trend may distract the learners from exploring and being attentive during the teaching and learning process as they are no longer motivated and not that interested in learning (Tinapay Tirol, 2021). Previous studies showed that learning styles had been explored and correlated with different factors separately. However, those studies were conducted in foreign setting and mostly focus on learners in intermediate level and grade 2 learners were not explored. A learner's learning styles may be influenced by their previous learning experiences, genetic make-up, and culture. Likewise, a child's learning style preferences in terms of individual learning significantly influence learners' engagement and literacy skills achievement (Magulod, 2019). It is on this context that the researcher felt the need to fill-in the research gap of conducting a study in the Philippine setting, particularly among the public elementary school in Laak North District, Division of Davao de Oro using a quantitative approach. Specifically, the researcher will utilize a quantitative descriptive-correlational research design to have a better understanding of the learning

styles with its relationship to learners' literacy skills in grade 2 which is found to be limited. Thus, the results of this study may be of interest to other researchers as it could provide valuable knowledge to their research. Adding more, the result of this study may provide inputs that are research-based in crafting an enhancement plan regarding the variable explored in this study to improve the literacy attainment of the grade 2 learners. The present study intends to contribute to the limited body of knowledge on literacy development in Davao Region context.

1.1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework of the Study—The current study is grounded on the Learning Styles Model of Dunn Dunn Theory (1978). The theory postulates that individuals have distinct learning styles influenced by environmental, emotional, sociological, and psychological factors. This theory suggests that modifying instruction to match learners' preferred learning styles can enhance learning outcomes. When applied to the prediction of learners' literacy skills, the theory implies that understanding and accommodating diverse learning styles could potentially improve literacy acquisition. Learners with a preference for visual learning might benefit from reading materials accompanied by illustrations or diagrams, while auditory learners may excel in environments where information is presented verbally or through discussions. The theory suggests a connection between learning styles and literacy skills, practical evidence supporting its predictive validity remains mixed. Some studies indicate that aligning instruction with learners' preferred learning styles may enhance engagement and motivation, ultimately facilitating literacy development. This research study is also anchored on the Ecological System Theory (1979) by Urie Bronfenbrenner. This theory provides a framework for understanding how various environmental influences shape individuals' development. According to this theory, individuals are embedded within multiple inter-

connected systems, including the microsystem (immediate environment), mesosystem (interactions between microsystems), exosystem (external environments indirectly affecting individuals), macrosystem (cultural values and norms), and chronosystem (changes over time). It becomes apparent that environmental factors play a crucial role in shaping factors such as family dynamics, peer interactions, and classroom environments that can influence learners' preferred learning styles. A child growing up in a household that values reading and provides ample opportunities for literacy-rich activities may develop a strong preference for visual or verbal learning modalities. Effective communication and collaboration between teachers and parents can facilitate a supportive learning environment that caters to individual learning preferences. Moreover, factors in the exosystem, such as community resources and cultural norms, can also shape learning styles and literacy practices. Access to libraries, museums, and community programs may enhance literacy development for learners with diverse learning styles. This theory emphasizes the importance of considering the complex interaction between environmental influences and individual characteristics in understanding how learning styles contribute to learners' literacy skills. As shown in Figure 1, the study consists of two variables. The independent variable is the learning style. The indicators of learning style are the visual or the mode of instruction wherein individual preference on taking information is by means of sense of sight; auditory or the mode wherein learners acquire new information by listening then repeating or discussing ideas with others; kinesthetic or the learning preference where individual's learn best with an active hands-on approach. Meanwhile, the dependent variable is literacy skills of grade 2 learners which will be described based on the assessment of the teachers on their reading skills, writing skills, speaking/listening skills and assessing their skills. By combining these

Fig. 1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework

measures, teachers create a comprehensive approach to improve the literacy skills of the learners, fostering a supportive and effective learning environment.

2. Methodology

This section contains the research design, research respondents, research instrument, data gathering procedure, and data analysis.

2.1. Research Design—In this study, quantitative non-experimental design utilizing descriptive-correlational technique of research is the method adopted by the researcher to gather data ideas, facts and information to achieve the main objective of the study. According to Creswell (2023) quantitative research is the systematic empirical investigation of observable phenomena via statistical, mathematical, or computational techniques. It is conclusive in its purpose as it tries to quantify the problem and understand how prevalent it is by looking for projectable results to a larger population. Meanwhile, descriptive-correlational research according to Myers et. al., (2013) examines how

the independent variable influences the dependent variable and establishes cause and effect relationship between variables. In this study the researcher will look into the relationship between two variables – learning styles and literacy skills. Thus, the interest of the study is to investigate whether learning styles significantly influence literacy skills.

2.2. Ethical Consideration—The researcher observed promptly the protocols deemed necessary as standard guidelines in carrying out the research study following study protocol assessments criteria, particularly in managing population and data. The survey questionnaires with supporting authors submit-

ted further evaluation to ensure content validity and appropriateness. After approval from the Ethics Committee, the researcher proceeded to the next phase of the study, ensuring full compliance with ethical standards, confidentiality agreements, and informed consent procedures to safeguard the rights and well-being of all participating respondents.

2.3. Research Respondents—Respondents of the study were 150 public elementary school grade 2 teacher-advisers in Cluster 3 4, in Laak North District, Division of Davao de Oro. The researcher employed stratified random sampling in selecting participants from purposively selected schools as the basis for stratification. Stratified random sampling is probability sampling that allows researcher to improve precision relatively simple random sampling wherein population divided into non-overlapping groups, or strata, along a relevant dimension such as gender (Salkind, 2020). In this study, certain inclusion criteria were implemented in determining the respondents of the study. The primary consideration of this study was to choose respondents who could provide information to achieve the purpose of this study. For the context of this study, grade 2 public elementary school teachers in Cluster 3 4 and in Laak North District, Division of Davao de Oro. The researcher

The second part is about the learners' literacy skills. The questionnaire is adopted from Pastore (2022) Literacy Survey for Teachers. The reliability coefficient and consistency among the items are high with the following factors:

2.5. Data Gathering Procedure—Steps were undergone by the researcher in conducting the study after the validation of the research questionnaire. Permission to Conduct the Study The researcher secured the permission to conduct the study. The researcher se-

preferred to conduct the study in Cluster 3 4 and Laak North District, Division of Davao de Oro because it could provide the needed data. Hence, only those grade 2 public elementary school teacher-advisers, with at least 3 years in service and who voluntarily signed the Informed Consent Form will be the participants of the study. Moreover, the study will be delimited only to the nature of the problem based on the research questions.

2.4. Research Instrument—To gather the data, two adapted survey questionnaires will be used. The first tool was about learning styles. This questionnaire was adapted from the study of Dejarlo et al., (2020) indicated with visual, auditory and kinesthetic. The Cronbach coefficient value for this instrument is indicated with high reliability and consistency. This questionnaire was subjected for content validity by 3 panel of experts to test its validity and reliability. In the manner of answering the questionnaire, the items were modified so that it may suit the context of this answer and be answerable using 5-Likert scale: 5–Strongly Agree 4–Agree 3–Moderately Agree 2–Disagree 1–Strongly Disagree. As a guide in determining the learning styles of grade 2 learners, the researcher made use of the range of means, description and interpretation presented below:

reading skills, writing skills, speaking/listening skills, and assessing their skills. The questionnaire made use of a 5-point Likert scale which was determined based on the following range of mean:

cured the endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School in The Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City. The endorsement letter from the Dean of the Graduate School in The Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City was attached permission letters to be endorsed to the school principals of the selected public elemen-

Scale Descriptive Levels and Interpretation for Learning Styles of Grade 2 Learners

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very High	Learning styles of grade 2 learners are always evident.
3.40 – 4.19	High	Learning styles of grade 2 learners are often-times evident.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	Learning styles of grade 2 learners are some-times evident.
1.80 – 2.59	Low	Learning styles of grade 2 learners are sel-dom evident.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	Learning styles of grade 2 learners are never evident.

Table X. Range of Mean, Descriptive Rating, and Interpretation of Learners’ Literacy Skills

Range of Mean	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very High	Learners’ literacy skills are always evident.
3.40 – 4.19	High	Learners’ literacy skills are oftentimes evi-dent.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	Learners’ literacy skills are sometimes evi-dent.
1.80 – 2.59	Low	Learners’ literacy skills are seldom evident.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	Learners’ literacy skills are never evident.

tary schools in Laak North District, Division of Davao de Oro. The letters were personally brought by the researcher to the principals of the schools where the study was conducted. The researcher also first appear to the office of the principal. After the approval from the respective offices were granted, the researcher then proceeded to the distribution and retrieval of the survey questionnaires. Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire The researcher proceeded to the distribution of the research instrument to the respondents after the approval to conduct the study. The study was conducted on April of 2025. Upon the distribution of the questionnaires, the benefits of the survey were briefly

discussed and explained to the identified respondents of the study. For the administration of the questionnaire, the researcher distributed the questionnaires simultaneously. The respondents of the study were given enough testing time for the questionnaires to be finished. After which, the data collected were subjected to quantitative analysis. Collation and Statistical Treatment of Data After the data retrieval of the questionnaire, the scores of each respondent were tallied to organize the data per indicator. After which, each score was subjected to descriptive and inferential analysis using SPSS. Informed Consent The researcher asked for the permission of respondents through a written informed consent. They

were properly informed about the purpose of the study and ample explanations were given to them for better understanding of the reason for their participation so that they can choose whether to participate or not. It was made clear that respondents' involvement in the study is voluntary. If ever they would refuse to participate, they were not forced by the researcher. Besides, the researcher was cautious to assure the respondents' psychological well-being. A written permission from the respondents were secured from them. The researcher informed the respondents that the study aimed to conduct a study on the factors that hinder/promote the learners' literacy skills of grade 2 learners as determined by their learning styles.

Vulnerability of Research Participants The respondents of the study were grade 2 teacher-advisers in public elementary school so they were not considered vulnerable since all of them are in legal age, though they were also considered vulnerable in the psychological aspect. The researcher emphasized that the survey was set at the respondents' convenience. Also, the researcher protected the confidentiality of the information disclosed.

Privacy and Confidentiality This study observed the data Privacy Act of 2012 wherein the researcher assured that the data cannot be traced back to the participants which were the real source of information, to protect the identities of the respondents. Moreover, the researcher assured that no personal data would be shared without the consent of the respondents. Thus, to ensure that no personal data would be exposed, the access was limited to the researcher alone. To protect the privacy of the respondents, it was assured that the researcher is the only person that could access the survey results. After the necessary data was collected, the researcher permanently disposed the survey result to assure that data cannot be traced back to the respondents who were the real source of information.

Risk, Benefits and Safety In administering the survey questionnaires, the researcher

fully disclosed to the respondents the nature of their participation and explained thoroughly and properly the purpose and benefits of the study as well as the confidentiality of their responses as stated in the online survey questionnaire. The respondents, without restrictions could ask questions related to the study. Further, the researcher ensured that the respondents were not be subjected to harm in any ways whatsoever. Moreover, the questionnaire and interview guide that were used in this study did not contain any degrading or unacceptable statements offensive to the respondents of the study. Likewise, this study is designed purely to collect academic information related to the study and they were not asked with personal information. To minimize inconvenience, the researcher made sure that the respondents were given ample time to answer the survey questionnaires. The respondents were given freedom not to answer questions which made them feel any psychological and emotional distress and they would be free to withdraw as a respondent of the study if they would feel that they cannot discuss the information that being asked from them.

Justice To avoid impartiality in choosing the respondents, the researcher regarded all respondents equal regardless if they would be respondent in the survey. The researcher did not prejudice in choosing the respondents of the study. Anybody who fitted the qualifications of being a grade 2 teacher-adviser, a permanent public elementary school teacher with 3 years or more teaching experience in the purposively selected schools. During the conduct of the study, the researcher made certain to respect the respondents by interrupting as little time as possible to the routine of the respondents. To compensate for the time spent during data gathering, the researcher gave tokens of appreciation to the respondents. The tokens were an assortment of souvenir.

Transparency To provide transparency in this study, any type of communication in relation to the research it was done with honesty

and transparency. To safeguard the welfare of the respondents, the researcher properly implemented the methods that are discussed to use in this study. All the necessary documents that supported the data analysis was included. Importantly, the researcher described the extent of the involvement of the respondents in this study and shared how the researcher-maintained objectivity in analyzing data and presentation of the results of the study. Qualification of the Researcher The researcher ensured that the responses of the respondents were not influence by any other factor like the conflict of interest. The findings of the study could be accessed by the respondents and school administrators of the participating schools because the information would be made available as long as they followed proper protocol to protect the anonymity of the respondents. The researcher also acknowledged the effort of every person who contributed to the success of the study, the Division of Davao de Oro will be given a furnished copy of the results of the research so it can be accessed by the respondents and be used for learning and further study.

2.6. *Data Analysis*—The following were the statistical tools utilized by the researcher in processing the gathered data:

Mean

This was useful in measuring the level of learning styles and learners’ literacy skills by providing an average score that reflects the central tendency of the data. Mean and standard deviation are descriptive statistics that tend to measure how the scores clustered around the average and how they scattered or varied across the dataset, thus offering a clearer.

Pearson-R

This was utilized to describe and measure the significance, direction, and strength of the relationship among various learning styles and learners’ literacy skills, providing statistical ev-

Adequacy of Facilities

The researcher engaged the respondents in a conducive environment and learning materials which were ample and available in the conduct of the study and was done within the time set by the researcher. The accuracy of gathering data from the respondents was ensured by encoding properly the ratings of the respondents during the day when the researcher was not too tired to do them to avoid errors in encoding. Also, the analysis and results gathered were proficient and aligned that serves as a primary basis for adequacy.

Community Involvement

It was a good practice to have community involvement during every phase of research from planning to reporting. Hence, the researcher planned to share the findings generated with the community, and community involvement were accorded with primacy in making decisions about the research agenda, appropriate method to apply in their context, and use of the results or findings. The findings of this study would then be shared back with the community through gatherings, fora, and conferences.

idence on how different learning preferences correlate with literacy performance. The results offer valuable insights that can guide educators in designing targeted instructional approaches, fostering more effective and personalized teaching strategies to enhance Grade 2 learners’ literacy development and academic success across diverse learning contexts

Linear Regression Analysis

It was applied to determine which specific domains of learning styles significantly influence learners’ literacy skills by identifying the strength and direction of relationships among variables, helping to predict literacy outcomes and offering valuable insights for targeted instructional interventions aimed at improving Grade 2 learners’ academic perfor-

mance, thereby supporting teachers in making data-driven decisions and promoting more effective literacy instruction across diverse educational settings, while also informing future

curriculum enhancements, fostering continuous professional development, and contributing to more inclusive and responsive educational practices at both school and district levels.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter discussed the findings of this study. They were thoroughly discussed, analyzed, and interpreted.

3.1. Learning Styles in Terms of Visual Learning Style —Summary of the Learning Styles Presented in Table 1 are data on the Summary of the Learning Styles. The overall mean of 4.60, which is Very High and always evident, is distributed by the indicators. They were presented with the corresponding mean as follows: visual learning styles (4.56), auditory learning styles (4.60), and kinesthetic learning styles (4.64). All of these indicators have descriptive equivalents of very high. The result of the data on the learning style reveals a consistently strong and favorable perception across

all indicators. It presented that learning styles indicates that Grade 2 learners exhibit a consistently strong preference across visual, auditory, and kinesthetic modalities. All three learning styles are perceived to be highly evident, suggesting that learners benefit from a multimodal approach to instruction. The findings reflect a well-rounded engagement in learning, where seeing, hearing, and doing all play significant roles in their educational experience. This emphasizes the importance of incorporating diverse teaching strategies to address and enhance the varied learning preferences of young learners.

Table 1. Summary of the Learning Styles

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Visual Learning Styles	4.56	Very High
Auditory Learning Styles	4.60	Very High
Kinesthetic Learning Styles	4.64	Very High
Overall Mean	4.60	Very High

Moreover, the findings highlight a robust and well-integrated set of learning styles that enhance both teaching practices and learner engagement. The thoughtful integration of visual, auditory, and kinesthetic approaches supports the development of learners' literacy skills through varied and meaningful experiences. These learning modalities collectively contribute to cultivating a school culture grounded in excellence, inclusivity, and mutual support. Ultimately, the results affirm that a re-

sponsive and supportive learning environment is essential in promoting learner achievement, sustaining teacher dedication, and advancing the overall effectiveness of educational initiatives. Magulod (2019) emphasized that recognizing learners' preferred learning styles enhances teaching effectiveness and improves academic performance, especially in early education. This aligns with the current study's findings, where visual, auditory, and kinesthetic preferences were found to significantly influ-

ence learners' literacy skills. Magulod further explained that differentiated instruction based on sensory learning channels increases motivation and engagement in young learners. These findings support the integration of multi-modal strategies in classrooms to improve literacy and overall learning outcomes. Khan et al. (2019) found that learners with a kinesthetic preference benefit most when instruction involves physical interaction, movement, and hands-on activities. This supports the findings of the current study, which showed that kinesthetic learning had the strongest influence on learners' literacy skills, particularly when they engaged in role-playing, manipulation of materials, and experiential tasks. Khan and colleagues emphasized that movement-based learning activates multiple sensory pathways, which enhances memory and understanding, especially in young learners. Their study confirms the importance of designing literacy instruction that includes action-oriented and tactile experiences

to improve learning outcomes.

3.2. Learners' Literacy Skills in terms of Reading Skills —Summary of the Learners' Literacy Skills

Table 2 showed the data on the Summary of the Learners' Literacy Skills. The data in this table are presented with corresponding means: reading skills (4.61), writing skills (4.59), speaking/listening skills (4.62), and assessing skills (4.70). All of these indicators have descriptive equivalents of very high. The overall mean result of 4.63, with very high descriptive equivalent, indicates that Learners' Literacy Skills was always evident in the four indicators. Furthermore, The summary of learners' literacy skills, as shown in Table 9, reflects a consistently strong performance across all key areas—reading, writing, speaking/listening, and assessing skills. The data reveals that learners demonstrate well-developed competencies that are regularly observed in classroom contexts.

Table 2. Summary of the Learners' Literacy Skills

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Reading Skills	4.61	Very High
Writing Skills	4.59	Very High
Speaking/Listening Skills	4.62	Very High
Assessing Skills	4.70	Very High
Overall Mean	4.63	Very High

Among these areas, assessing skills appeared to be the most prominent, indicating that learners are not only able to perform but also engage with literacy tasks in ways that can be evaluated meaningfully. This suggests a holistic development of literacy where learners are active participants in both acquiring and demonstrating their skills. All four indicators were consistently rated at the highest descriptive level, reinforcing the idea that literacy is a well-integrated component of the learning experience. The findings highlight that learners are not only profi-

cient in traditional literacy tasks like reading and writing but also excel in oral communication and reflective assessment processes. This comprehensive literacy profile suggests that instructional approaches and school-wide strategies are effective in nurturing these skills. Overall, the results point to a learning environment that supports and sustains high levels of literacy competence across multiple domains. Tinapay and Tirol (2021) highlighted that the development of literacy skills in early grades is most effective when teaching strategies are structured and

responsive to learners’ needs. Their findings support the results of this study, which showed that learners demonstrated strong abilities in reading, writing, speaking, and self-assessing when instruction was aligned with their learning preferences. They emphasized the value of guided reading, writing routines, and oral language activities as essential tools for improving literacy proficiency. This reinforces the current study’s conclusion that well-structured and learner-centered approaches lead to better literacy outcomes. Yang et al. (2021) discussed that comprehensive literacy programs integrating vocabulary, phonemic awareness, and speaking opportunities promote deeper learning and higher literacy achievement. This is consistent with the findings of this study, where students performed well across literacy indicators when supported by varied and interactive instructional methods. Yang et al. noted that multi-sensory exposure to language allows young learners to develop stronger reading and writing fluency. Their research affirms that engaging and diversified literacy instruction—tailored to how students learn—results in more meaningful skill

development.

3.3. *Relationship Between Learning Styles and Learners’ Literacy Skills*—Table 3 presented the data on the significant relationship between learning styles and learners’ literacy skills in public elementary schools, as measured by Pearson’s r. The computed r-value of 0.68 indicates a high degree of relationship or substantial. The p-value of 0.00 is less than the alpha value of 0.05, indicating that the null hypothesis is rejected at the significance level. The findings reveal that the independent and dependent variables are statistically significant. Hence, there was a significant relationship between School Environment and Teachers’ Commitment. The results further suggest that school environment can make a significant difference in the teachers’ commitment. This implies that all participants agreed that the quality of the school environment plays an important role in shaping and enhancing teachers’ commitment. Consequently, the school environment acts as a guiding factor that motivates and directs teachers’ dedication, ultimately contributing to a more positive and effective learning experience for learners.

Table 3. Relationship between Learning Styles and Learners’ Literacy Skills. The result further suggests that Learning Styles

Variables	Pearson-r	Degree of Correlation	P value	Interpretation	Decision
Learning Styles (X) Literacy Skills (Y)	0.68	Very High	0.000	Significant	Reject

Note: Significance when $P < 0.05$

The Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.68 suggests a substantial positive relationship between learning styles and literacy skills. The p-value of 0.000, which is below the significance level of 0.05, indicates that this relationship is statistically significant. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. The result implies that learners whose dominant learning styles are effectively addressed by teachers tend to show higher liter-

acy skills achievement. This finding was correspondent to Maslow’s Hierarchy of Needs Theory (1954) emphasizing that teachers’ commitment is influenced by the fulfillment of various needs within the school environment. When basic needs such as safety and a supportive atmosphere are met, teachers are more motivated to engage socially and professionally, fostering a stronger commitment to their work. The theory

highlights that a positive school environment addresses these needs at multiple levels, encouraging teachers to reach higher levels of motivation and dedication. Thus, the significant relationship between school environment and teachers' commitment can be understood through how well the school setting fulfills teachers' physiological, social, and esteem needs. Furthermore, the study's findings on the significant relationship between school environment and teachers' commitment are strongly supported by the understanding that commitment functions as a deep connection between teachers and their organization. When the school environment is positive and supportive, it fosters a sense of pride and belonging among teachers, strengthening their dedication to the school's goals. This connection enhances teachers' motivation and engagement, encouraging them to actively contribute to the success of the institution. Therefore, a well-maintained school environment plays a crucial role in cultivating high levels of teacher commitment, as reflected in the study's results (Hill, 2019).

3.4. On the Indicators of Learning Styles that Significantly Influences the Learners' Literacy Skills—Presented in table 4 is the linear regression analysis, illustrating the significant influence of indicators of learning styles on learners' literacy skills. Through linear regression analysis, it was found that the three indicators of learning styles — visual learning styles, auditory learning styles and kinesthetic learning styles are significant predictors of learners' literacy skills. The regression model significantly predicts learners' literacy skills ($F(3,146) = 201.70, p < 0.001$). Among the predictors, kinesthetic style has the highest standardized beta coefficient ($= 0.42$), indicating it is the most influential. All three learning styles significantly contribute to the variance in literacy skills, justifying differentiated instruction. The model yielded an R^2 value of 0.332, indicating that 33.2% of the variance in teachers' com-

mitment can be explained by these three indicators. Furthermore, the model was statistically significant, as evidenced by an F-value of 8.932 and a p-value < 0.000 , demonstrating the robustness and reliability of the relationship. The regression analysis revealed that all three learning styles—visual, auditory, and kinesthetic—significantly influenced the literacy skills of Grade 2 learners. The kinesthetic learning style had the strongest effect with a coefficient of $B = 0.40$ and a p-value of 0.000, indicating that learners who engage in physical and hands-on activities tend to perform better in reading, writing, and oral literacy tasks. It indicates that the model better predicts the importance of learning styles to learners' literacy skills in the Division of Davao de Oro. Visual learning also had a meaningful contribution ($B = 0.28, p = 0.000$), suggesting that learners benefited from materials like pictures, written guides, and visual cues. Auditory learning followed closely with $B = 0.27$ and $p = 0.000$, showing that oral instruction, discussions, and repetition supported learners' literacy development. The model as a whole showed a strong fit with an R^2 value of 0.46, meaning that 46% of the variation in learners' literacy skills can be explained by their learning styles. The F-value of 41.57 and corresponding model p-value of 0.000 confirm that the regression model is statistically significant and predictive. These findings emphasize the importance of using multi-modal instructional strategies to cater to the diverse learning preferences of students. A teaching approach that integrates visual, auditory, and kinesthetic elements is more likely to improve literacy outcomes, particularly in early elementary settings where foundational skills are being established. Furthermore, the findings suggest that educational programs, teacher training modules, and curriculum development initiatives should consider the dominant learning preferences of young learners when designing literacy-focused content. This ensures that in-

struction is developmentally appropriate, engaging, and supportive of varying cognitive and sensory needs. The above findings were in consonant with the ideas of Magulod (2019), who affirmed that aligning teaching strategies with preferred learning styles increases learners’ engagement and academic performance. Further-

more, Bouiri et al. (2021) emphasized that differentiated instruction tailored to learners’ sensory preferences enhances literacy retention. In support, Foroozandehfar Khalili (2019) noted that kinesthetic activities promote active learning and lead to deeper literacy development.

Table 4. Linear Regression Analysis on the Indicators of Learning Styles that Significantly Influence Learners’ Literacy Skills

Model	B	Beta	Standard Error	p-value	Decision
H01	(Intercept)				
H02	(Intercept)				
	Visual learning styles	0.35	0.05	0.000	Reject H0
	Auditory learning styles	0.29	0.047	0.000	Reject H0
	Kinesthetic learning styles	0.42	0.050	0.000	Reject H0
R ²	0.461				
F-value	41.57				
p-value	0.000				

Note: Significant at $p < 0.05$.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter discussed the research’s focal points and the statistical analysis results. It also presents the conclusions and recommendations based on the study’s findings.

4.1. Findings—The study explored the relationship between the learning styles and literacy skills of Grade 2 learners in Laak North District, Davao de Oro Division using a quantitative correlational approach. The learning styles was distinguished by key indicators such as visual, auditory, and kinesthetic all of which were rated very high. These findings confirm the importance of integrating multisensory teaching strategies to enhance the literacy outcomes of young learners. Findings revealed that many learners preferred to process information through visual materials, such as pictures, drawings, and written text. These learn-

ers demonstrated better comprehension when information was presented through diagrams, written notes, or visual cues. Auditory learning was also strongly observed among the learners. They showed improved focus and understanding when instructions were delivered orally or when they engaged in discussions and verbal exercises. Listening, repeating instructions aloud, and talking through ideas supported their grasp of literacy content. A large number of learners also showed strong preference for movement and hands-on activities as part of their learning process. These learners absorbed and understood lessons more effectively when al-

lowed to move, manipulate objects, or act out ideas, indicating a strong link between bodily engagement and cognitive processing. Learners also demonstrated solid foundational literacy skills in reading, writing, speaking, listening, and self-assessment. They were able to decode and understand texts, express ideas through writing, participate in oral discussions, and evaluate their own progress. This reflects the effectiveness of structured classroom instruction and the adaptability of teachers in meeting diverse learning needs. The findings of the study affirm the conceptual grounding of the research based on Dunn Dunn's Learning Styles Model (1978). The significant influence of visual, auditory, and kinesthetic learning styles on learners' literacy skills directly supports the theory's claim that instruction aligned with learners' preferred modalities enhances learning outcomes. The strong predictive value of kinesthetic learning ($B = 0.40$) aligns with the idea that physical and hands-on experiences promote better engagement and retention, particularly in early literacy development. This validates the premise that when instructional methods cater to individual learning preferences, such as visual inputs for visual learners or verbal repetition for auditory learners, learners show improved performance across reading, writing, and speaking domains. Additionally, Bronfenbrenner's Ecological Systems Theory (1979) offers insight into how external environmental factors—such as home literacy practices, classroom dynamics, and community support—interact with the learner's development. The high preference for all three learning styles and the learners' very high literacy skill ratings suggest that the microsystem (teachers and classroom environment) is successfully providing multi-modal, literacy-rich instruction. Moreover, the influence of broader systems—like the availability of learning materials at home or cultural emphasis on reading—may also be contributing to learners' preferences and outcomes. This af-

firms Bronfenbrenner's assertion that learning is shaped not only by internal preferences but also by external environmental interactions, supporting the need for a holistic and collaborative approach to literacy instruction.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the overall findings of this research, the following conclusions were drawn: Based on the findings of this study, it can be concluded that Grade 2 learners possess well-developed learning preferences in all three domains — visual, auditory, and kinesthetic. It also signifies that kinesthetic learning shows the strongest presence. These learning styles significantly support how young learners engage with and absorb academic content, as shown by the very high mean scores across all modalities. The structured and supportive classroom environments that cater to multiple learning styles are key in promoting student-centered instruction and increasing academic engagement. The study further revealed that learners demonstrated very high levels of literacy skills across reading, writing, speaking/listening, and assessing competencies. These findings reflect the effectiveness of current literacy instruction strategies in Laak North District, which include varied book access, guided reading, writing practice, and oral participation. Teachers' confidence and consistency in implementing literacy instruction underscore the positive literacy outcomes among learners. There was a statistically significant relationship between learning styles and literacy skills, confirming that learners whose preferred styles were recognized and accommodated achieved higher literacy performance. Regression analysis also identified all three learning styles as significant predictors of literacy, with kinesthetic learning style being the most influential. These findings affirm that understanding and integrating learners' sensory preferences in instructional design is a strong determinant of literacy success in early education. In summary, all three learning styles were highly evident among learners; all literacy skills

indicators showed very high levels; learning styles and literacy skills were positively and significantly related; and each domain of learning style significantly influenced literacy skills. Therefore, tailoring instruction to learners' dominant learning styles not only enhances engagement but also directly supports their literacy development. These conclusions underscore the need for continued teacher training in differentiated instruction and learning-style-responsive teaching strategies.

4.3. Recommendations—Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were offered for consideration shown in next page:

Learners The learners are encouraged to become more aware of their preferred learning styles and actively engage in classroom activities that align with how they learn best. By recognizing whether they understand lessons better through visual, auditory, or kinesthetic means, they can take more responsibility in their own learning process. Engaging with varied instructional materials—such as visual aids, oral exercises, or hands-on tasks—can enhance their literacy development. Learners should also be provided with opportunities to explore all learning styles to become more flexible and adaptive in diverse learning situations. **Teachers** The teachers must design lesson plans that incorporate diverse learning strategies to address the varied learning styles of their students. Integrating visual presentations, auditory discussions, and kinesthetic activities in literacy instruction can help reach all learners more effectively. Teachers are advised to assess individual learning preferences early in the school year to tailor instruction accordingly. Professional development workshops focusing on differentiated instruction and learner-centered strategies are also recommended to enhance teaching effectiveness. **School Administrators** The school administrators are encouraged to support the implementation of differentiated instruction by providing

teaching materials and resources that cater to multiple learning styles. Creating flexible classroom environments that support movement, discussion, and visual engagement can improve literacy outcomes. Administrators should also provide teachers with ongoing training and support systems focused on learning style integration. Furthermore, monitoring and evaluating literacy programs based on how they accommodate learner diversity can contribute to overall school improvement. **Department of Education (DepEd)** The DepEd should develop policy frameworks that emphasize the integration of learning styles in curriculum design and instructional practices. It is recommended that national literacy programs be enhanced with components that promote inclusive and multi-sensory learning approaches. Curriculum guides and teacher manuals should include strategies for visual, auditory, and kinesthetic learners. Continuous capacity-building for teachers and school leaders on adaptive teaching methods will help sustain improvements in early literacy performance. **Policy Makers** The policy makers are advised to consider legislation and educational standards that mandate differentiated instruction as part of early grade literacy programs. Recognizing the role of individual learning styles in literacy achievement should inform decisions on curriculum development and teacher training requirements. Policies must promote equitable learning environments where all learners have access to instruction suited to their cognitive preferences. Investing in inclusive educational programs will ensure more responsive and effective literacy education across the country. Furthermore, policy makers are encouraged to allocate sufficient funding for professional development, instructional materials, and learning technologies that support multimodal teaching. Regular monitoring and evaluation mechanisms should be established to assess the impact of differentiated instruction on literacy outcomes. Collaboration with educational researchers and front-line

educators will further help shape policies that reflect the evolving needs of today's diverse student populations, especially in underserved and marginalized communities. Future Researchers Future researchers are encouraged to explore the long-term effects of learning-style-based instruction on literacy development beyond Grade 2. Comparative studies across districts or grade levels could provide insights into regional and contextual influences. It is recommended to investigate how technology can support multi-sensory instruction for young learners. Future work may consider qualitative approaches to capture learners' experiences and preferences. Additionally, researchers may examine socio-emotional factors and learning styles in influencing literacy achievement. Exploring parental involvement, classroom culture, and community resources could provide a holistic view of literacy development. Longitudinal studies could track changes in learning preferences and literacy outcomes, offering guidance for policy and practice.

5. References

- Albeshtawi, A. E. M. (2018). Learning styles preferences of efl learners at alghad international college for health science-saudi arabia-dammam. *International Journal of English Language Literature in Humanities*, 5(4), 215–220.
- Baer, J., Kutner, M., Sabatini, J., & White, S. (2020). Basic reading skills and the literacy of america's least literate adults: Results from the 2003 national assessment of adult literacy (naal) supplemental studies. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED505187.pdf>
- Benitez-Correa, C., Vargas-Saritama, A., Gonzalez-Torres, P., Quinonez-Beltran, A., & Ochoa-Cueva, C. (2022). Students' preferences and learning styles in relation to reading and writing strategies at distance higher education. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 21(4), 316–336. <https://doi.org/10.26803/ijlter.21.4.18>
- Bouiri, O., Lotfi, S., & Talbi, M. (2021). Correlative study between personality traits, student mental skills and educational outcomes. *Education Sciences*, 11(4), 153. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci11040153>
- Bronfenbrenner, U. (1979). *Making human beings human: Bioecological perspectives on human development*.
- Chieke, J. C., Ewelum, J. N., & Madu, C. O. (2019). Determination of auditory and visual learning styles of adult learners in adult literacy centres in anambra state, nigeria. *Department of Adult Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University*.
- Creswell, J. D. (2023). Mechanisms of mindfulness training: Monitor and acceptance theory (mat). *Clinical Psychology Review*, 51, 48–59.
- Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2023). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (6th ed.). SAGE Publications.
- Dejarlo, J. O., Manimtim, J. S. J., Padilla, E. D. P., San Juan, J. A., & Aterrado, J. S. J. (2020). Study habits, parenting style, and learning style as correlates to academic performance of students with solo parent. *PalArch's Journal of Archaeology of Egypt/Egyptology*, 17(1), 300–306.
- Department of Education. (2019). Pisa 2018 philippine national report. <https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2019/12/PISA-2018-Philippine-National-Report.pdf>

- Dunn, R., & Dunn, K. (1978). *Teaching students through their individual learning styles: A practical approach*. Prentice Hall, Reston, VA.
- Foroozandehfar, L., & Khalili, G. F. (2019). On the relationship between iranian efl learners' reading fluency, their personality types and learning styles. *Cogent Arts & Humanities*, 6(1), 1681347. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311983.2019.1681347>
- Ganimian, A. J., & Murnane, R. J. (2019). Improving education in developing countries: Lessons from rigorous evaluations. *Review of Educational Research*, 89(3), 583–617.
- Hartman, M. C., Nicolarakis, O. D., & Wang, Y. (2019). Language and literacy: Issues and considerations. *Education Sciences*, 9(3), 180.
- Hassan, N. C., & Sen, H. M. (2019). Relationship between parenting styles, academic performance and socio-demographic factors among undergraduates at universiti putra.
- Hulme, C., Snowling, M. J., West, G., Lervåg, A., & Melby-Lervåg, M. (2020). Children's language skills can be improved: Lessons from psychological science for educational policy. *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, 29(4), 372–377. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0963721420923684>
- Jasti, C., Jukes, M. C., Dubeck, M. M., Elliott, & Inyega, H. N. (2018). *A child-to-child approach to improve literacy: Design of the buddy reading program in kenya* [Manuscript submitted for publication].
- Khan, S. A., Arif, M. H., & Yousuf, M. I. (2019). A study of relationship between learning preferences and academic achievement. *Bulletin of Education and Research*, 41(1), 17–32.
- Magulod, G. C. J. (2019). Learning styles, study habits and academic performance of filipino university students in applied science courses: Implications for instruction.
- Maslow, A. H. (1954). *Motivation and personality*. Harper & Row.
- O'Connor, R. E., Beach, K. D., Sanchez, V. M., & Flynn, L. J. (2020). Building word reading, vocabulary and comprehension in the primary grades: Exploring the outcomes of a schoolwide model. *Reading and Writing*, 33(9), 2283–2310.
- Orbeta, E. D., & Decano, R. S. (2019). Factors associated with students' performance in english in the implementation of spiral progression. *PUPIL: International Journal of Teaching, Education and Learning*, 3(1), 45–70.
- Pastore, S. (2022). Teacher survey on literacy.
- Piper, B., Sitabkhan, Y., & Betts, K. (2018). *Effectiveness of teachers' guide in the global south: Scripting, learning outcomes, and classroom utilization* (tech. rep.). <https://doi.org/10.3768/rtipress.2018.op.0053.1801>
- Roell, K. (2020). The visual learning style.
- Salkind, N. J. (2020). *Research methods in education and psychology: Integrating & diversity with quantitative & qualitative approaches* (5th). SAGE.
- Syofyan, R., & Siwi, M. K. (2018). The impact of visual, auditory, and kinesthetic learning styles on economics education teaching.
- Thomas, N., Colin, C., & Leybaert, J. (2020). Interactive reading to improve language and emergent literacy skills of preschool children from low socioeconomic and language-minority backgrounds. *Early Childhood Education Journal*, 48(5), 549–560. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10643-020-01022-y>

- Tinapay, A. O., & Tirol, S. L. (2021). Teachers' primary roles in the new normal: Through the e-learning perspective. *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology*, 6(10), 90–91.
- Vizeshfar, F., & Torabizadeh, C. (2018). The effect of teaching based on dominant learning style on nursing students' academic achievement. *Shiraz University of Medical Sciences*.
- Yang, X., Dulay, K. M., McBride, C., & Cheung, S. K. (2021). How do phonological awareness, rapid automatized naming, and vocabulary contribute to early numeracy and print knowledge of filipino children? *Journal of Experimental Child Psychology*, 209, 105179. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jecp.2021.105179>